

THE IMAGE OF NATIONAL LANGUAGE LANDSCAPE OF THE WORLD

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Annotatsiya

This article provides feedback on the language and its linguistic landscape. Reflecting the worldview determines the level of authorship and creative authorship. Each author has a unique approach to understanding and describing the world.

Kalit so'zlar: Language, universe, linguistic, landscape, communicative, image, physiological.

INTRODUCTION

Every language has a separate worldview, and a linguist is obliged to compose the content of expressions in accordance with that landscape. It reflects a person's unique perception of the world, which is reflected in language. Language is an important factor in the formation and existence of human knowledge of the universe. This set of knowledge, sealed in linguistic forms, is called the Linguistic Landscape of the Universe. The concept of worldview (also linguistic) is based on the study of human perceptions of the universe. The linguistic view of the universe shapes man's relationship to the world (nature, animals, himself. Any natural language reflects a certain way of knowing the world.) The unique socio-historical experience of the community from a single person is a characteristic feature of the national languages recorded. Literature analysis and methodology If the idea of the diversity of the world's landscape has been expressed relatively recently, the idea of the existence of a distinct linguistic view of the universe was expressed by W. von Humboldt as early as the beginning of the nineteenth century. In the research of some authors, the hypothesis of linguistic relativity has gained serious significance, first of all, in the works of D. Alford, J. Carroll, D. James and other authors. In this, the teachings of Sefhir and Wharf are significantly supplemented. In particular, D.H. James introduces another principle of functional relativity of languages. According to him, there are differences between languages in the nature of their communicative functions. The term "worldview" has only recently become the subject of scientific and philosophical thought, and was coined in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries in the field of physics. One of the founders of the theory of the world landscape, M. Planck discovered the practical and scientific landscapes of the universe. He connected the human perception of existence with the first kind of landscape.

Discussion and results

The linguistic landscape of the universe is created through a variety of colors, including mythology, figurative metaphorical words, similes, connotative words, stereotypes, symbols, and so on. Each language embodies a system of national characteristics that define the worldview of the speaker and shape the world. Phraseology plays a special role in creating a linguistic picture of the world. They are the "mirror of people's lives." The nature of phraseological units and their knowledge are closely related to the life experience and cultural and historical traditions of the people who speak the language. The semantics of phraseological units focuses on the description of man and his activities. Humboldt wrote: It requires a higher and common purpose, such as the study of the unseen. " In a number of literary genres, man is the main object of study.

CONCLUSION

In short, the study of the linguistic landscape of the universe is closely related to the conceptual landscape of man and his life, his relationship with the world, the conditions of his existence. The linguistic landscape of the universe interprets the different world landscapes of man and reflects the general world landscape. In this regard, it is worth quoting the following words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan IA Karimov on the national and cultural features of our language: let's take phrases that enrich and complement with no-content. Strange as it may seem, it is difficult to translate these phrases into other languages. It should be noted that these concepts are not just sweet words invented by someone, but pleasant words. Such notions are a practical expression of the great values that have emerged over the centuries as the basis of the worldview and spiritual life of our people, deeply rooted in our consciousness. relationship is closely related to the question of the conceptual view of the universe, which reflects the conditions of its existence. The linguistic landscape of the universe interprets the different world landscapes of man and reflects the general world landscape.

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